

The Relationship among Employees' Performance, Employees' Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment: A Research Jumhouria Banks in Libya

Orhan Küçük¹, Ali Bridan²

¹Faculty of Applied Sciences, Sakarya University, Sakarya, Türkiye.

²Faculty of Economics and Commerce, Al Marqab University, Khoms, Libya.

Email address:

alibridan@yahoo.co.uk (ALI), orhankucuk@subu.edu.tr (ORHAN)

Received: 7 Nov 2021, Revised: 15 Nov 2021, Accepted: 9 Dec 2021, Online: 30 Dec 2021

Abstract

Organizations in both the private and public sectors around the world rely on their workforce for optimum productivity, which results in organizational efficiency. Employee satisfaction plays a vital role in contributing to reducing negative behaviors such as frequent absenteeism in the workplace, lack of discipline in performance, and high turnover. The success of any organization depends on the performance of its employees. Increasing organizational commitment among employees is an important aspect of improving performance. Studies are carried out to increase performance in organizations. What can be done to increase organizational commitment with performance is a research topic that managers and researchers are interested in. The results of the research show that the objective component of commitment is related to the desired results regarding employee satisfaction. The aim of this study is to reveal the relationship between employee satisfaction, employee performance and organizational commitment in Libya Jumhouria Banks. 55 data collection tools were used for bank employees and 85 data collection tools were used to learn the opinions of customers in banks. The study data were collected by face-to-face questionnaire method with 140 people. The result of the analysis revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance of Jumhouria Banks in Libya. Detailed analysis showed that the link between job satisfaction and organizational performance is stronger than the link between organizational performance and job satisfaction. The study will serve as a policy guide for the management of the Libyan banking sector in areas related to improving employee performance through job satisfaction, and will also accelerate work in the field of organizational behavior and human resource management.

Keywords: Employees, Performance, Employees Performance, Employee Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment.

1. Introduction

The world is rapidly transforming due to globalization, economic growth, instability and the advancement of information

technology, which affects the way people conduct business (Shrivastava & Purang, 2009). The current global changes have

created a competitive platform among many organizations around the world. Therefore, organizations need to face these challenges and changes in the external environment because employees represent valuable organizational assets that help organizations advance and achieve their goals. According to Saner and Eyupoglu (2015), banks as financial institutions serve as the nation's economy's backbone, directly impacting its development. Thus, maintaining the highest job satisfaction among employees and human resources is vital for the nation's growth and performance (Jie, Hasan, & Bidin, 2018).

Inuwa (2016) observed that Departments in different institutions rely on effective methods to motivate employees to achieve organizational goals efficiently and effectively. Therefore, employee performance is the biggest challenge for organizations in general. Howard (2009) Note that job satisfaction is a combination of different desired and unwanted behaviours of an individual within the organization which motivate him to perform work according to his job satisfaction. Job satisfaction symbolizes how optimistic employees are with rewards and benefits.

2. Literature Review

Satisfaction means the acceptance of a satisfactory product, service, transaction, or other action encountered. Internal customer satisfaction defined as the situation in which the employee feels happy about his job. His perception is satisfactory as a whole with the working environment, employment, authorities, and responsibilities (Küçük, 2016: 320).

Job satisfaction is one of the most important reasons for contributing to workers' negative and positive behaviours in institutions. This issue has received significant attention on the organizations' part due to increased performance and individuals' loyalty to their organizations .

Sabbagha, Martins, and Ledimo (2018) reported that understanding the factors that contribute to an individual's job satisfaction imperative when related to bank employees (Naseer, ul Haq, & Farooq, 2018). Furthermore, Muindi (2011) realized that Job satisfaction is the determinant of business success in various state institutions. Performance is the amount of output produced by a specific enterprise, unit, or employee with an acceptable standard infrastructure or qualifications in terms of the sector in a certain period (Küçük, 2017: 233).

Based on the definition of performance as the amount of output produced in a certain period, employee performance is the amount of the production related to the job or area of responsibility delivered in a certain period by employees with the appropriate technical and social equipment. (Küçük, 2020: 44).

According to Janssen (2001), employees see the fairness between effort and reward, leading to increased satisfaction in response to moderate levels of job requirements. Kucharska and Erickson (2019), indicated that the improvement in organizational performance results from the committed workforce that feels satisfied with their work in organizations. Furthermore, Siengthai and Pila-Ngarm (2016) find that companies should enhance employee job satisfaction while implementing job redesign; thus, job redesign improves employee performance. Based on the above discussion, the following hypothesis has suggested by H1: There is a significant relationship between employee performance and job satisfaction.

The performance of the employee is the basis for the success of any organization to reach its goals. Enhancing organizational commitment among the employees is an essential aspect of improving performance. According to Thamrin (2012), organizational commitment has a

significant influence on employees' performance. The study revealed that organizational commitment dimensions jointly and independently influence employees' performance among academic staff (Folorunso, Adewale, & Abodunde, 2014). Furthermore, Rafiei, Amini, and Foroozandeh (2014), In their studies, emphasized that the three dimensions of organizational commitment, affective commitment, continuity, and normative commitment have had a significant positive impact on job performance. Besides, the results showed that job performance is related to employee commitment.

Organizational commitment; Employees identify themselves with the organization and coincide with some values in a mental sense, the vision of the organization encompasses the employees' view of life. As a result, they feel belonging to the organization. They explain their continuing work with commitment rather than dependency, other values that keep them there and establish a strong bond to serve the organization (Küçük, 2020: 69).

Siu (2003) found a strong correlation between job commitment and job performance. Despite the positive relationship of emotional and normative commitment to the job, the performance was less distinct on transformational behaviour levels between the two variables. (Sungu, Weng, Hu, Kitule, & Fang, 2020).

According to Sungu, Weng, and Xu (2019), transformational leadership affects the relationship between affective organizational commitment and employees' job performance. High professional commitment contrasts with its impact on employees with low professional commitment. Based on the above discussion, the following hypothesis has proposed by H2: There is a significant relationship between employee performance and organizational

commitment.

Researchers are intrigued by how organizations can develop a commitment to one set of terms but not necessarily to another stage. Evidence suggests that the objective component of commitment is related to desired outcomes related to the job) Meyer, Paunonen, Gellatly, Goffin, & Jackson, 1989). Thamrin (2012), demonstrated that organizational commitment has a significant favourable influence on Job satisfaction. Eliyana and Ma'arif (2019), in their study, found that leadership has a direct effect on job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Gunlu, Aksarayli, and Perçin (2010) confirmed that job satisfaction dimensions do not significantly impact continuance commitment among the managers of large-scale hotels. Other studies, including, Srivastava (2013) found that Job satisfaction is positively related to Organizational Commitment. Based on the above discussion, the following hypothesis has proposed H3: There is a significant relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

3. Research Design and Approach

The purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between employee performance, employee satisfaction, and organizational commitment.

The study followed the quantitative approach in collecting data through a questionnaire distributed to various respondents. According to M. Bhatti and Sundram (2015), Quantitative research is a method to calculate the data through statistical analysis and represents the result of the analysis figures explaining the specific search problem. Forza (2002) reported that probabilistic sampling is a procedure that can be used in the random selection of the study population so that each unit of the population has the opportunity to choose. Accordingly, the questions used to measure variables on the

Likert scale. Employee performance is improved Küçük (2020a), employee satisfaction Küçük (2020b), and organizational commitment by Küçük (2020c).

Quantitative data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. The researcher distributed (170) questionnaires to employees of the banks under study. (153) valid questionnaires have retrieved for analysis, and 5 of the questionnaires returned were invalid due to incomplete and indifferent responses making 153

sufficient, accurate, and used for analysis. Therefore, it constitutes 90% of the total responses, and on this basis. The interpretative study enables examining and interpreting relationships between variables, particularly cause-and-effect connections (Wisker, 2008).

4. The Research Model

The research framework shows the relationship between employee performance, employee satisfaction, and organizational commitment in Jumhouria Banks in Libya.

Figure 1. Research Model

5. Data Analysis

Table 1. Factor Analysis of Employees Satisfaction

Job Satisfaction	Factor Load	Eigen value	Variance	Cronb. Alfa	Average	KMO
4. Employees have faith in the performance appraisal system.	.695	3.38	64.69	.770	2.99	.610
11. The compensation for all employees is directly linked to his/her performance.	.673				3.31	
1. The duties of each job are clearly defined	.656				2.46	
5. Employees have more than one potential opportunity for promotion.	.609				2.44	
7. Job security is almost guaranteed in this job.	.562				2.44	
10. If the bank were facing economic problems, employees would be the last to get cut in employment.	.532				2.12	
3. It is challenging to dismiss an employee in the job	.512				3.77	
2. Employees are permitted to suggest improvements in the way they work	.473				2.46	
8. In our bank, compensation is decided based on the competence or ability of the employee.	.479				2.69	
9. Employees are encouraged to have open communications with their superiors in the bank	.507				3.21	
12. Employees in this bank are allowed to participate in decisions affecting them.	.628				2.49	
6. Performance-based incentives and bonuses are available to all employees.	.464				3.74	

Cronbach's alpha is a measure used to assess the reliability, depending on the Cronbach's alpha, the $0.800 > \alpha > 0.60$ scale is very reliable. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin was used to test the variables' suitability in the factor analysis and test the sample size (KMO; 0,610). Two factors have an intrinsic value on the Kaiser criterion for a single element. However, the result showed deviations that would justify retaining only one factor explaining 64.686% of the variance. The Cronbach's

Alpha, which showed reliability in the test, was found to be 0.770.

Factor loadings were greater than 0.4, eigen value was greater than 1, and KMO was 0.610 (> 0.5). Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient was determined as 0.770. Hence, the scales appear to be quite reliable. Therefore, the scale is correct and dependable, scientific research and analysis, indicating homogeneity and increased credibility (Küçük, 2016).

Table 2 Factor Analysis of Employees Performance

Employees Performance	Factor Load	Eigenvalue	Variance Exp Rate (%)	Cronbach's alpha	Average	KMO value
24. I feel encouraged to come up with new and better ways of doing things.	.670	3.637	65.909	.784	3.31	.652
17. There are formal training programs to teach new employees the skills they need to perform their jobs	.662				2.99	
14. Job performance is an essential factor in determining the incentive compensation of employees.	.644				2.46	
18. The job description for each job contains all the primary duties performed by the individual employees.	.617				2.44	
13. Employees in this job can expect to stay as long as they wish.	.593				2.55	
20. Employees are provided with performance-based feedback and counselling.	.536				2.43	
23. I could clearly define quality goals in my work.	.491				2.12	
22. My skills and abilities have used within the bank.	.492				3.21	
21. The Bank does an excellent job of keeping employees informed about matters affecting us.	.500				2.69	
15. Each employee is aware of a clear career path in this bank.	.455				2.46	
16. Each job in our bank has a clear job description	.544				3.77	
19. Performance evaluation system aims at the bank to discipline the employees rather than improving their performance.	.286				3.75	

Statistics related to employee performance factors and an analysis of explanatory factors that reveal the surveyed participants' loading factors have presented in Table 2. This result illustration the quality of being higher than 0.60. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy is within acceptable limits ($p < 0.000$). Factor analysis performed on 12 main components. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure verified the sampling adequacy for the analysis $KMO = 0.652$. Initial investigations have achieved to obtain eigenvalues of each factor. One factor had an eigenvalue over Kaiser's criterion, and the scree plot was straightforward and showed inflexions that would justify retaining only one factor that explained 65.909% of the variance.

Table 3 shows the factor loadings after rotation. Consequently, Through the tables shown from the statistical analyses, it is possible to represent the employee performance measure by one factor only (Küçük, 2016). Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy is within acceptable limits ($p < 0.000$). Factor analysis has performed on 12 items. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure verified the sampling adequacy for the examination, $KMO = 0.652$.

In this situation, the value of (α) for the correct value indicates that homogeneity and then reliability, and conversely, whenever the value of (α) approaches zero, this indicates heterogeneity, leading to lack of credibility. The table below shows

the reliability analysis for the Employees Performance scale. This scale had high reliability, Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.784$. The Cronbach's Alpha, which showed reliability in the test, was found to be 0.784. As a result, the scales seem to be

quite reliable. Therefore, the scale used is valid and dependable as it indicates the consistency and increased reliability used in the research (Küçük, 2016, pp. 227-232).

Table 3. Factor Analysis of organizational commitment

Organizational Commitment	Factor Load	Eigenvalue	Variance	Cronbach's alpha	Average	KMO
7. Leaving the bank and looking for another job will affect my life	.795	3.18	67.62	.713	2.89	.820
4. I feel like 'part of the family' at my organization.	.773				3.21	
6. I have too few options to consider leaving my organization	.670				2.35	
2. I would be happy to spend my career with my organization.	.612				2.89	
8. Right now, I must stay with my organization.	.582				2.14	
3. My organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.	.545				2.10	
9. It would be costly for me if I leave my organization now.	.514				3.89	
1. I feel 'emotionally attached' to my organization.	.454				2.59	
10. It would be tough for me to leave my organization right now, even if I wanted to.	.432				2.36	
5. I am proud to be one of the members of my organization.	4.12				2.74	

Table 3 shows the organizational commitment factors' statistics and an analysis of the explanatory factors for them.

The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin measure verified the sampling adequacy for the examination, KMO = 0.820. A preliminary investigation has performed to obtain the eigenvalues of each factor. One factor had an eigenvalue over Kaiser's criterion, and the scree plot was straightforward and showed inflexions that would justify retaining only one factor that explained 67.62% of the variance. Table 3 shows the factor loadings after rotation.

The factor analysis of the organizational commitment scale indicates that It may represent only one factor (Küçük, 2016). Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy is within acceptable limits ($p < 0.000$). According to the Cronbach reliability scale, factor analysis performed on (10) principal components, and the result was $\alpha = 0.713$. The Cronbach's Alpha, which showed reliability in the test, was found to be 0.713. As a result, the scales seem to be quite reliable. Therefore, this scale adopted for its validity and reliability, where homogeneity analyses indicate reliability (Küçük, 2016: 227-232).

Table 4. Correlations Between Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance, and Organizational Commitment

CORRELATIONS		1	2	3
Employee Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.974**	.720**
Employee Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.974**	1	.815**
Organizational commitment	Pearson Correlation	.720**	.815**	1

Correlation analysis has analyzed relationships between employee performance, employee satisfaction, and organizational commitment. The statistical scale used to measure the relationship between the three variables is the correlation coefficient. Correlation analysis is primarily concerned with knowing whether a relationship exists and within determining its magnitude and direction. At the bottom of Table 3 shows correlation significant at the 0.01 level (Pagano, 2012).

The study found the product to have a statistically significant and positive relationship between the two variables, where a correlation between employee performance and employee satisfaction. 0.974**. In this case, employee performance and employee satisfaction. is a statistically significant relationship between the likelihood and the tendency. Therefore, the H1 hypothesis is accepted.

Likewise, It found a strong relationship between employee performance and organizational commitment equal to 0.720**, which main there is a statistically significant and positive relationship (Küçük, 2016). In this case, there is a statistically significant relationship between employee performance and organizational commitment. Therefore, the H2 hypothesis is accepted.

The results of the study showed that there is a statistically significant relationship between the job satisfaction variable and the organizational commitment variable. about 0.815** (Küçük, 2016). satisfaction

and organizational commitment. Therefore, the H3 hypothesis is accepted.

6. Results

This research aims to review the literature on employee performance and job satisfaction at Jumhouria Banks in Libya. This research aims to review what has written about employee performance, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment in Jumhouria Banks in Libya.

Moreover, it highlighted the relationship between variables and job satisfaction within alternative strategies based on the previous literature. Besides, this research explores employee performance and its relationship to job satisfaction and job performance. a questionnaire to collect the required data about the three variables used in his study. This data collection tool included a symbolic and systematic question on research issues. The study analyzed all data using SPSS software.

This research showed the importance of study variables, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment to improving employee performance in the organizations under study.

They are highlighting the concepts of job satisfaction and organizational commitment and their role in improving employee performance. Highlight the potential relationships between employee performance, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment, in addition to providing a detailed explanation of the

ideas related to the concept of employee performance and searching for ways to measure it. Eventually, the result shows a positive statistically significant relationship between employee performance, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment in Jumhouria Banks Libyan.

7. Discussion and Suggestions

The research focused on investigating the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment and their role in improving employees' performance within Jumhouria banks in Libya. This study reached some conclusions of them, showed a Pearson correlation analysis of the existence of a statistically significant and positive relationship between the three variables of the survey "employee job satisfaction and commitment to organizational performance." This result agrees with Dessler (2010) that Employee satisfaction helps the organization reach its goals to achieve competitive advantages. Our findings also support by Dessler (2010), K. K. Bhatti and Qureshi (2007), and Crossman and Abou-Zaki (2003). They argue that Their previous studies showed a significant correlation between employee satisfaction and work performance.

Moreover, these studies prove that employees who are satisfied with their jobs perform better compared to others. This result supports the results of our research, according to Gu and Siu (2009). This study discussed employee performance, job satisfaction, and finding a positive relationship between them. The findings of current research support the claim that job satisfaction helps connect an individual with an organization through organizational commitment. The study also revealed a strong relationship between work performance and organizational commitment. This finding is supported by both (Angle & Lawson, 1994; Cesário &

Chambel, 2017; Nazir & Islam, 2017; Setyaningrum, Setiawan, Surachman, & Irawanto, 2017).

Job satisfaction, job performance, and organizational commitment are extremely vital determinants of an organization's success, effectiveness, efficiency, and success. These variables are still receiving apparent attention from researchers for decades due to their importance in organizations' success. These variables are essential to consider when deciding by the organization's management to achieve their desired goals and objectives.

Most of the research indicates that organizations should be aware of employee needs to improve the organizational environment to help them achieve a competitive advantage. This study focuses on the duty to stimulate human resources to work hard, efficiently, and effectively to achieve staff's highest satisfaction. The research focuses on the need to involve workers in adopting decisions and drawing the organization's policies. The researcher recommends the necessity of adopting policies and strategies that work to create an organizational environment dominated by employee satisfaction with their jobs and reflected on organizational commitment to them. These are the functions of human resource management.

8. References

- [1]. Angle, H. L., & Lawson, M. B. (1994). Organizational commitment and employees' performance ratings: Both type of commitment and type of performance count. *Psychological reports*, 75(3_suppl), 1539-1551.
- [2]. Bhatti, K. K., & Qureshi, T. M. (2007). Impact of employee participation on job satisfaction, employee commitment and employee productivity. *International review of business research papers*, 3(2), 54-68.
- [3]. Bhatti, M., & Sundram, V. P. K. (2015). *Business research: Quantitative and*

- qualitative methods: Kuala Lumpur: Pearson Malaysia Sdn Bhd.
- [4]. Cesário, F., & Chambel, M. J. (2017). Linking organizational commitment and work engagement to employee performance. *Knowledge and Process Management*, 24(2), 152-158.
- [5]. Crossman, A., & Abou-Zaki, B. (2003). Job satisfaction and employee performance of Lebanese banking staff. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*.
- [6]. Dessler, A. E. (2010). A determination of the cloud feedback from climate variations over the past decade. *Science*, 330(6010), 1523-1527.
- [7]. Eliyana, A., & Ma'arif, S. (2019). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment effect in the transformational leadership towards employee performance. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 25(3), 144-150.
- [8]. Folorunso, O., Adewale, A., & Abodunde, S. (2014). Exploring the effect of organizational commitment dimensions on employees performance: An empirical evidence from Academic Staff of Oyo State Owned Tertiary Institutions, Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4(8), 275.
- [9]. Forza, C. (2002). Survey research in operations management: a process-based perspective. *International journal of operations & production management*, 22(2), 152-194.
- [10]. Gu, Z., & Siu, R. C. S. (2009). Drivers of job satisfaction as related to work performance in Macao casino hotels. *International journal of contemporary hospitality management*.
- [11]. Gunlu, E., Aksarayli, M., & Perçin, N. Ş. (2010). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment of hotel managers in Turkey. *International journal of contemporary hospitality management*.
- [12]. Howard, M. C. (2009). Emotional intelligence as a predictor of job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and occupational commitment among human service workers. Capella University.
- [13]. Inuwa, M. (2016). Job satisfaction and employee performance: An empirical approach. *The Millennium University Journal*, 1(1), 90.
- [14]. Janssen, O. (2001). Fairness perceptions as a moderator in the curvilinear relationships between job demands, and job performance and job satisfaction. *Academy of management journal*, 44(5), 1039-1050.
- [15]. Jie, C. T., Hasan, N. A. M., & Bidin, R. (2018). JOB SATISFACTION AMONG EMPLOYEES: AN INVESTIGATION OF GOVERNMENT-LINKED BANK INSTITUTION IN MALAYSIA. *Jurnal Kemanusiaan*, 16(1).
- [16]. Kucharska, W., & Erickson, G. S. (2019). The influence of IT-competency dimensions on job satisfaction, knowledge sharing and performance across industries. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*.
- [17]. Küçük, O. (2016). Bilimsel araştırma yöntemleri. Ekin Yayınları.
- [18]. Meyer, J. P., Paunonen, S. V., Gellatly, I. R., Goffin, R. D., & Jackson, D. N. (1989). Organizational commitment and job performance: It's the nature of the commitment that counts. *Journal of applied Psychology*, 74(1), 152.
- [19]. Muindi, F. K. (2011). The relationship between participation in decision making and job satisfaction among academic staff in the school of business, university of Nairobi. *Journal of Human Resources Management Research*, 2011, 1-34.
- [20]. Naseer, M., ul Haq, A., & Farooq, M. (2018). Antecedent of Employees' Career Satisfaction: An Empirical Investigation of Pharmaceutical Sector of Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(7), 281-299.
- [21]. Nazir, O., & Islam, J. U. (2017). Enhancing organizational commitment and employee performance through employee engagement. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*.
- [22]. Pagano, R. R. (2012). *Understanding statistics in the behavioral sciences (Vol. 1)*: Cengage Learning.
- [23]. Rafiei, M., Amini, M., & Foroozandeh, N. (2014). Studying the impact of the organizational commitment on the job performance. *Management science letters*, 4(8), 1841-1848.
- [24]. Sabbagha, M. D. S., Martins, N., & Ledimo, O. (2018). Conceptual Model of Employee Motivation and job Satisfaction for Staff Retention Practices in Foreign Exchange Banking Context. Paper presented at the ICMLG 2018 6th International Conference on Management Leadership and Governance.
- [25]. Saner, T., & Eyupoglu, S. Z. (2015). The job satisfaction of bank employees in North Cyprus. *Procedia economics and finance*, 23, 1457-1460.

- [26]. Setyaningrum, R. P., Setiawan, M., Surachman, S., & Irawanto, D. W. (2017). Employees Performance; Leadership, Organizational Commitment and Trust. *International Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 11(2).
- [27]. Shrivastava, A., & Purang, P. (2009). EMPLOYEE PERCEPTIONS OF JOB SATISFACTION: COMPARATIVE STUDY ON INDIAN BANKS. *Asian Academy of Management Journal*, 14(2).
- [28]. Siengthai, S., & Pila-Ngarm, P. (2016). The interaction effect of job redesign and job satisfaction on employee performance. Paper presented at the Evidence-based HRM: a Global Forum for Empirical Scholarship.
- [29]. Siu, O. I. (2003). Job stress and job performance among employees in Hong Kong: The role of Chinese work values and organizational commitment. *International journal of psychology*, 38(6), 337-347.
- [30]. Srivastava, S. (2013). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment relationship: Effect of personality variables. *Vision*, 17(2), 159-167.
- [31]. Sungu, L. J., Weng, Q., Hu, E., Kitule, J. A., & Fang, Q. (2020). How Does Organizational Commitment Relate to Job Performance? A Conservation of Resource Perspective. *Human Performance*, 33(1), 52-69.
- [32]. Sungu, L. J., Weng, Q., & Xu, X. (2019). Organizational commitment and job performance: Examining the moderating roles of occupational commitment and transformational leadership. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 27(3), 280-290.
- [33]. Thamrin, H. (2012). The influence of transformational leadership and organizational commitment on job satisfaction and employee performance. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 3(5), 566-572.